

FIBER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Michael J. Salkind Ph.D.
Chief, Structures and Materials
Sikorsky Aircraft
Stratford, Connecticut 06602, U.S.A.

Current Affiliation:

Director, Product Development
AVCO Systems Division
Lowell, Massachusetts 01850

This paper traces the pertinent design considerations and applications for composites and attempts to project future developments. In addition to the design complexity introduced by the anisotropic behavior, lack of yielding, and the unique fatigue and fracture behavior of composites, the strong interaction of design, manufacturing and material processing is discussed. Structural applications are grouped according to structural concept type in an attempt to explain the evolution of each type. Recent emphasis on cost and performance improvement rather than weight reduction and the changing character of attachments is discussed.

Anticipated future developments include a peaking and perhaps a reduction in use of composites for sporting goods, but a steady growth in aerospace to the point at which, in one or two decades at the most, the majority of aircraft structural weight will be composites. Technology developments necessary to meet this goal include designing for low-cost manufacture, standardizing materials, acquisition of service experience, and development of structural reliability, safety, and maintainability criteria and procedures.

Introduction

Naturally occurring and man-made fiber composites have been used since the dawn of man. Yet the vigorous development of these material is only one decade old. The present resurgence of interest in composites has been brought about by the advent of boron, graphite, and, most recently Kevlar*^R fibers, and by the rediscovery of glass fibers for highly loaded structures. This development has been motivated primarily by aerospace applications, but the use of composites for sporting equipment, high-speed machinery, automobiles, and other non-aerospace structures has come to dominate a very rapidly growing market.

This paper will trace the pertinent design considerations and applications for composites and attempt to project future developments for a technology that within a short time has moved from infancy to a contracted period of maturation.

The early concerns of making a composite structure lighter and structurally adequate are now articles of faith. As with all technological developments, these concerns are giving way to considerations of reduced cost, improved system productivity, and improved safety, reliability, survivability, and maintainability. These considerations, then, will dominate future design and manufacture. Without doubt, they will result in practices radically different from what we have known in the past.

Design Considerations

In the past decade, initial interest in composite structures stemmed largely from the availability of materials with very high stiffness and strength coupled with low density. Although these properties still remain outstanding design considerations, time has shown us that other attributes of composites make them even more valuable. Two have become outstanding in importance. I refer to the ability to tailor the structural properties of a material in different directions and to the ability to mold a composite structure into a complex shape at relatively low cost. The first attribute allows the designer a new degree of freedom: he can design the material and the structure simultaneously, and he can use the material most efficiently. He can develop completely new structural concepts, otherwise impossible or impractical with isotropic materials. The second attribute, the ability to mold in complex shapes, also gives the designer a new degree of freedom: he is almost free of shape restrictions imposed by limitations on metal forming and cutting. He is, thus, free to design in new ways, unhampered by most earlier constraints.

*Trade Mark of DuPont

This revolution in design and manufacture is illustrated schematically in Figure 1. The design procedure for metals involves selection of a single material from a finite catalog of materials to meet a design concept requirement. This often involves compromise, since the metals have particular fixed stiffness characteristics. For example, the commonly used aircraft structural materials - steel, titanium, and aluminum - have elastic modulus values of 30, 16, and 10 million psi respectively. But, what if the optimal design for an airfoil of specified aerodynamic geometry and aeroelastic characteristics requires a material with a tension modulus of 20 million psi and a torsional modulus of 2 million psi? There is no such metal. Of necessity, the design must be compromised to use one of the metals. Once the design is released for manufacture, metal stock is procured in the form of a forging, bar-stock, plate, or a casting. This involves consideration of procurement and inventory costs and lead times. Finally, the stock is cut to the finished shape. It is not unusual for some stock to require a one year lead time for procurement, and it is ironic that often 90% of the stock finds itself on the shop floor as expensive metal chips.

As seen in Figure 1, the process is dramatically different for composites. Instead of selecting a material from a finite number of possibilities, the designer can tailor the material in essentially infinite ways. He can choose individually the fiber, matrix, fiber content, and laminate orientation that will provide the stiffness or strength required, in the desired direction and in the desired location.

The design function itself is greatly changed and expanded. A team of people must combine its capabilities in structural design, materials, analysis, and fabrication to achieve the desired result. Indeed, many aerospace companies have established separate departments or teams for composite structures. Because it is most efficient to place fibers in the exact location and orientation to react principal loads, more precise data are needed for determination of loads and for structural analysis. Also, the design of the laminate itself implies the use of iterative computer programs. This has led to extensive use of sophisticated computer techniques, especially finite-element analysis, for composite structures.

The manufacturing process is also profoundly altered by the use of composites. Because the laminate and structural design essentially define the manufacturing sequence, the initial design concept must consider producibility aspects, and manufacturing personnel must be members of the design team. In fact, many of the recent development programs in composites involve design of structures based on using simpler, lower-cost processing and tooling.

Fig. 1 - DESIGN OF COMPOSITES IS SIGNIFICANTLY DIFFERENT FROM METALS

FIG. 3 - COMPOSITES EXHIBIT LARGE ANISOTROPY AND SENSITIVITY TO SHEAR. (REF. 1).

FIG. 2 - LAMINATE FAILURE CRITERION IS BASED ON THE WEAKEST LAMINA. AFTER HACKMAN (REF. 3.)

Procurement, inventory, and machining costs are also significantly different for composites. Instead of procuring different stock for almost every part, as is the case with metals, many composite structures can be made from the same pre-impregnated tape or broadgoods. Lead time for these materials is generally one to two months, compared with one year and more for some metal forgings or plate stock.

Automated machinery for composite tape and broadgoods lay-up is still in the developmental stages, but it has already demonstrated higher speeds and lighter weight than metal-cutting machines. This is so because such machines do not have to exert the large forces necessary to cut metals. Also, because the composite material is layed up in nearly the finished form, scrap material is small, only 10 to 20% of that of metals. One current limitation is the accuracy of the composite tape made for such machines.

DESIGN PROCEDURES

The unique characteristics of composites make designing with them quite different from designing with metals. These characteristics include the lack of plastic yielding, the nearly elastic stress-strain behavior, the large number of elastic coefficients required to define a coupled anisotropic laminate, the importance

of laminate stacking sequence, interlaminar shear stresses, problems of attachments, response to stress concentrations, the flat characteristic of the fatigue S-N curve, and the slow accumulation of fatigue damage accompanied by stiffness change. The techniques for designing with composite materials are well documented (References 1-15), so the present discussion will be limited to review of a few highlights.

Consider the tensile stress-strain behavior of boron-epoxy, Figure 2. The nearly linear behavior to fracture and lack of plastic yielding is typical for most composites (for example boron, graphite, and glass) but not for Kevlar, which, in compression exhibits plastic behavior similar to that of metals. The two laminae seen in Figure 2, 0° and 90° , exhibit significantly different ultimate strengths, but when combined into a single laminate ($0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$) exhibit an intermediate ultimate strength. There are several criteria for establishing design allowables (see Section 4.1.5 of Reference 1). For the example shown in Figure 2, the laminate is considered to have failed (Laminate design ultimate stress) when the weakest lamina reaches its ultimate strain, even though this is considerably below the laminate ultimate strength. The design limit stress for the laminate is established by the strain at which the weakest lamina reaches two-thirds of its ultimate.

The significant anisotropy of composites substantially complicates the design and analysis process. As seen in Figure 3, a single unidirectional lamina exhibits a strength parallel to the fibers that can be an order of magnitude larger than the transverse strength. For the case shown, boron/epoxy, the compression strength is considerably larger than the tension strength. The opposite is true for glass, graphite, and Kevlar/epoxy composites, however, because of the micro-instability of these fibers, which are smaller in diameter. In addition, a lamina is made up of two components, fiber and matrix, which can shear relative to one another. For this reason, the imposition of an in-plane shear stress can change the anisotropic failure envelope, as noted by the dashed line in Figure 3.

The discussion thus far has considered the anisotropy within a single unidirectional lamina. Unless the stacking sequence is selected to result in a balanced laminate when several laminae are combined into a laminate, the in-plane shear strains in each layer will couple and cause interlaminar shear stresses that will create out-of-plane distortions of an unrestrained laminate. An example of interlaminar shear (Ref. 16) is seen in Figure 4, in which the photographs are of surface displacements of tension specimens made visible by using moire grids. The upper laminate, which is unidirectional, shows no coupling and a uniform surface displacement pattern. The lower laminate exhibits interlaminar shear, which shows up as non-uniform displacement at the specimen edges. The net result of the three-dimensional anisotropy and coupling is that

such a laminate requires eighteen elastic constants for a complete definition compared with two for an isotropic material.

FIG. 4 - INTERLAMINAR SHEAR CAN CAUSE LARGE EDGE DISTORTION. AFTER OPLINGER (REF. 16).

FIG. 5 - PROPER LAMINATE SELECTION CAN REDUCE HOLE STRESS CONCENTRATION AFTER SCHJELDERUP & PURDY (REF. 19).

FIG. 6 - STIFFNESS OF COMPOSITES DECREASES WITH FATIGUE DAMAGE.

Let me go on to consideration of the effects of load introduction. Anyone who has ever driven a nail close to the end of a piece of wood only to have the wood split is acquainted with the problem of load introduction into composite materials. The inability of many laminates to withstand a concentrated load satisfactorily has led to the use of adhesive bonds to spread the load over a large shear area. Such joints must be analyzed properly to keep peak shear stresses in the adhesive at reasonable levels (Ref. 17). Techniques such as tapering and insertion of lower modulus material in the adherends (Ref. 18) have been used successfully.

Although adhesive bonded joints are used extensively, they require a high degree of process control and sophisticated non-destructive inspection to achieve acceptable reliability. Such

controls are costly and, despite their use, do not always detect weak bonds. As a result we have seen an increase in the use of bonded and fastened joints and, more recently, mechanically fastened joints alone. The problem with mechanical fastening is illustrated by the upper curve in Figure 5 (from Ref. 19), which indicates the large sensitivity of the $[0_2/\pm 45]$ laminate to stress concentration. It is now recognized that stress concentration can be reduced to acceptable levels by tailoring the laminate in the vicinity of the hole. This can be accomplished by changing the local laminate orientation (the $[0/\pm 45/90]$ laminate of the lower curve in Figure 5), by inserting plies of lower modulus material (softening strips), by inserting metal shims (popular at first but falling into disuse because of cost and reliability problems), or simply by locally thickening the laminate.

The fatigue behavior of composites differs radically from that of metals in several important ways (Ref. 20). Whereas metals exhibit one failure mode - cracking - composites exhibit a variety of failure modes, including fiber-matrix debonding, delamination, fiber breakage, and matrix cracking. All can occur independently or interdependently. As seen in Figure 6, such damage can result in stiffness changes very early in the total life to fracture. Such behavior is desirable from the point of view of safety, but it leads to the requirement that fatigue design be based on a failure criterion other than fracture. A specified percentage stiffness change (for example, 5 or 10%) is a criterion that has been used.

Compared with metals, composites exhibit relatively flat S-N (stress vs. number of cycles to failure) fatigue behavior. As a result, composite structures have gained a well deserved reputation as being highly fatigue resistant. Indeed, few have failed in fatigue either in service or test. The metal machines used in fatigue tests usually fail before the composite test specimen. Yet this behavior must be carefully considered when designing for a spectrum of fatigue loading that includes a relatively small number of high load cycles. Whereas current practice for metals usually involves truncating a load spectrum to delete the large number of small loads (not damaging) and a small number of very high loads (causing yielding, therefore less damaging), the high loads are very significant for composites because they do not exhibit yielding. The result is that for composites, the static and low cycle loading requirements will dominate the design. This behavior presents the possibility of reducing the cost and time involved in qualification of a composite structure by static testing and fatigue testing using a substantially truncated test spectrum.

The relative sensitivity of composites to stress concentrations in fatigue generally is the opposite of our experience with metals. As seen in Figure 7, for example, aluminum (like most ductile metals) exhibits no sensitivity to a hole under static loading. Aluminum

does exhibit increasing sensitivity to the same stress concentration at higher cycles. Most composites behave in the opposite way. They are more sensitive to stress concentrations in static and low cycle fatigue loading and less so in high cycle fatigue (see Figure 7). This factor further reinforces the fact that static and low cycle fatigue loading dominates composite structural design.

AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

Today there are thousands of individual structural applications of composite materials in various stages of development or production. I will attempt to summarize a few of the representative items (Ref. 1, 3, 19, and 21-25 supply a more complete summary) in order to illustrate the historical development, prominent design considerations, and benefits obtained.

Early aerospace applications of composites were primarily for control surfaces to meet high stiffness requirements for avoidance of flutter and to realize the large potential saving of weight. The General Dynamics/U.S. Air Force F-111 horizontal stabilizer (Refs. 3, 26) is shown in Figure 8. It was one of the first of these components to reach flight status. The structure consists of boron-epoxy skins bonded to full-depth honeycomb core, with a bonded and bolted metal pivot attachment fitting and mechanically fastened boron and glass epoxy edge assemblies. One ship set weighs 842 pounds, which is a 300-pound (27%) weight reduction from the production metal stabilizers.

FIG. 7 - COMPOSITES AND METALS EXHIBIT OPPOSITE SENSITIVITY OF STRESS CONCENTRATION TO CYCLING.

FIG. 8 - THE BORON-EPOXY F-111 HORIZONTAL STABILIZER WAS ONE OF THE FIRST FLIGHTWORTHY COMPOSITE STRUCTURES. GENERAL DYNAMICS PHOTO.

The first production advanced composite structure (and the first to reach flight status) was the Grumman/U.S. Navy F-14 hori-

zontal stabilizer (Ref. 27), which has been in service successfully for several years. The structure consists of boron epoxy skins adhesively bonded to full-depth honeycomb core and adhesively bonded to a stepped metal pivot fitting. Edge fairings are aluminum. The structure weighs 19% less than its metal counterpart. The McDonnell-Douglas/U.S. Air Force F-15 also has vertical and horizontal tail surfaces with boron skins, as seen in Figure 9. The composite empennage is 25% lighter than a metal empennage and has been in service since 1972.

FIG. 9 - THE F-15 "EAGLE" HAS BORON-EPOXY SKINS ON THE VERTICAL AND HORIZONTAL TAIL SURFACES. McDONNELL DOUGLAS PHOTO.

FIG. 10 - GRAPHITE SKINS AND SUBSTRUCTURE WERE USED FOR AN EXPERIMENTAL A-4 STABILIZER. McDONNELL DOUGLAS PHOTO.

The McDonnell Douglas/U.S. Navy A-4 horizontal stabilizer (Ref. 28), seen in Figure 10 is substantially different from the previous examples. It has a composite rather than a full-depth honeycomb substructure. The skins are solid graphite-epoxy and are adhesively bonded and mechanically fastened to a substructure consisting of graphite-epoxy/honeycomb sandwich bonded shear webs. The structure is 28% lighter than the production metal part. A boron-epoxy skin, full-depth honeycomb core adhesively bonded rudder that is 37% lighter than its metal counterpart has been developed for the McDonnell Douglas F-4. A total of 45 rudders were manufactured and placed in service beginning in 1969 (Figure 11).

A graphite-epoxy upper aft rudder assembly for the McDonnell Douglas DC-10 will be placed into limited service beginning in 1975 (Refs. 21, 29, 30, 31). The structure consists of a one-piece molded graphite-epoxy skin and substructure assembly with mechanically fastened leading and trailing edges. The limited service program, sponsored by the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), has as its goal in-service flight evaluation of at least 11 composite rudder assemblies. They are not only lighter (approximately 35%), but are projected to be competitive in cost with current metal production parts.

The Lockheed/U.S. Air Force C-5A boron-epoxy wing slat (Ref. 32), seen in Figure 12, has been in service on 11 aircraft and has accumulated more than 18,000 flight hours through mid-1974. The structure consists of boron/honeycomb core sandwich that is bonded to metal and composite formers. The composite structure weighs 22 percent less than the aluminum slat and has one-tenth the number of components.

FIG. 11 - FORTY-FIVE BORON-EPOXY RUDDERS HAVE BEEN IN SERVICE ON THE F-4. McDONNELL DOUGLAS PHOTO.

FIG. 12 - THE C-5A WING SLAT HAS BEEN IN SERVICE ON 11 AIRCRAFT. FIGURE COURTESY OF LOCKHEED AIRCRAFT.

FIG. 14 - MORE THAN ONE HUNDRED GRAPHITE 737 SPOILERS ARE IN COMMERCIAL SERVICE. BOEING CO. PHOTO.

FIG. 13 - TWO 707 BORON FOREFLAPS HAVE BEEN IN SERVICE SINCE 1970. BOEING CO. PHOTO.

The Boeing 707 wing foreflap (Ref. 33), seen in Figure 13 is a boron-epoxy skin/honeycomb core monocoque structure. Two such components, which are 25% lighter than the aluminum foreflap, have been in service since 1970 and have accumulated more than 22,000 flight hours. The Boeing 737 spoiler (Ref. 33), seen in Figure 14 is a graphite-epoxy skin, full-depth honeycomb core bonded structure.

It is 20% lighter than the aluminum production part. Under a NASA program, more than 100 spoilers have been in commercial airline service beginning in 1973, with more than 200,000 flight hours to date.

FIG. 15 - BOTH BORON AND GRAPHITE WING FLAPS HAVE BEEN DEVELOPED FOR THE A-4. McDONNELL DOUGLAS PHOTO.

FIG. 16 - THE RIB FOR THE A-4 FLAP IS MOLDED GRAPHITE. McDONNELL DOUGLAS PHOTO.

FIG. 17 - A CH-54 HELICOPTER WITH BORON-EPOXY REINFORCED ALUMINUM STRINGERS HAS BEEN IN SERVICE SINCE 1972. SIKORSKY AIRCRAFT PHOTO.

FIG. 18 - A BORON-EPOXY DOUBLER WAS USED TO INCREASE THE FATIGUE LIFE OF THE F-111 WING PIVOT FITTING. AFTER DIAL AND HOWETH(REF. 36).

The McDonnell Douglas/U.S. Navy A-4 wing flap, seen in Figure 15, has been made in two composite versions, boron and graphite (Ref. 31). The boron design consists of separate upper and lower boron skins bonded to full-depth honeycomb core and metal ribs and fittings. It weighs 27% less than the aluminum production component and contains 70% fewer parts. The graphite version has a one-piece

graphite skin, continuous around the trailing edge, bonded to the honeycomb core and with a molded graphite rib (Figure 16). It weighs 39% less than the metal part and contains 89% fewer parts.

A second category of structure that achieved early use exploits selective reinforcement of metal structure by adhesively bonded composite material. The concept was originated by NASA Langley researchers (Refs. 34, 35). The initial interest in this concept was avoidance of mechanical attachment to composites. To date, selective reinforcement has been used for three production aircraft, in all cases in order to strengthen or stiffen the original metal design to meet a greater requirement. The Sikorsky/U.S. Army CH-54 helicopter tail cone (Ref. 18), seen in Figure 17 has unidirectional boron-epoxy bonded to the vertical legs of each aluminum stringer and has been in service since 1972. The boron provides the stiffness required for dynamic tuning at one-fourth the weight of the equivalent aluminum. The General Dynamics/U.S. Air Force F-111 wing pivot fitting doubler (Ref. 36), seen in Figure 18 was incorporated to increase the fatigue life of the steel fitting. In addition to saving 11 pounds, the bonded boron fitting saved 21% in cost on new aircraft and 60% on retrofitted aircraft. Under NASA sponsorship, the Lockheed/U.S. Air Force C-130 wing box has been reinforced with boron-epoxy strips bonded to the caps of the aluminum stringers and to the aluminum skins inside the stringers. The change has extended the fatigue life at a weight saving of more than 500 pounds (Refs. 30, 32). Another application that involved use of selective reinforcement in the initial design is the Rockwell/U.S. Air Force B-1. Boron-epoxy was bonded to five metal major fuselage longerons to save more than 1000 pounds.

Fairings is a third category of structure to which composites have been applied extensively. For many years, glass-epoxy has been used for these lightly loaded structures, because they can be molded with complex curvature at lower cost than an equivalent aluminum structure. The Sikorsky H-53 cockpit canopy, seen in Figure 19, is among the largest and most complex of such structures. The glass-epoxy structure weighs approximately the same as its metal counterpart, but costs less than half as much. As a one-piece molding, it saves the large labor costs associated with assembling the many pieces of the metal structure.

Recently, Kevlar (formerly PRD-49) aramid fibers have been substituted for glass in many fairing structures in order to realize the weight saving inherent in the lower fiber density. Under NASA sponsorship, the components seen in Figure 20 have been in flight service on three commercial Lockheed L-1011 aircraft for more than one year. As of December 1974 these components had accumulated more than 10,000 total flight hours (Ref. 30). The Sikorsky/U.S. Army YUH-60A UTTAS helicopter contains more than 50 Kevlar fairings. It should be noted that Kevlar/epoxy is strong in tension but weak in compression, which somewhat limits its applicability. There is in-

dication that this limitation may be overcome by combining Kevlar with other filaments in a hybrid construction.

The Grumman/U.S. Navy F-14 overwing fairing (Ref. 37), seen in Figure 21, contains graphite and glass-epoxy skins with integrally molded boron-epoxy beam caps. The composite structure is 25% lighter than the equivalent metal structure and 40% less costly. The General Dynamics/U.S. Air Force F-111 has a graphite-epoxy wing pivot fairing that is 26% lighter than an aluminum fairing and 31% less costly (Ref. 36).

FIG. 19 - THE MOLDED H-53 COCKPIT CANOPY IS ONE-THIRD THE COST OF METAL STRUCTURE.

FIG. 20 - KEVLAR FAIRINGS ARE IN COMMERCIAL SERVICE ON THE L-1011. LOCKHEED AIRCRAFT PHOTO.

FIG. 22 - BORON-EPOXY CH-54 TAIL SKID TUBES HAVE BEEN IN SERVICE SINCE 1972. SIKORSKY AIRCRAFT PHOTO.

FIG. 21 - THE F-14 COMPOSITE OVERWING FAIRING IS 25% LIGHTER AND 40% LESS COSTLY THAN A METAL FAIRING. AFTER HADCOCK (REF. 37)

A fourth category of structure for which composites have found wide use is the truss, in which highly directional loading makes for efficient use of highly directional composite material. One of the first of these structures, which has been in service since 1972, is the boron-epoxy tail skid (Ref. 20) on the Sikorsky/U.S. Army CH-54 helicopter, seen in Figure 22. Each boron-epoxy tube is approximately one-third the weight of its aluminum counterpart and is bonded

and bolted to the metal end-fittings. The graphite-epoxy truss structure in the NASA Applications Technology Satellite (Figure 23) weighs only 80 pounds, half the weight of the original metal design (Ref. 38). In addition to the weight saving, a major motivation for use of graphite was the low coefficient of thermal expansion, which minimizes distortion of the structure in the temperature extremes of space. Other space applications for graphite epoxy, which exploit its low thermal expansion characteristics, include antennae for the Viking orbiter (Ref. 39), the ANIK communications satellite (Ref. 38), and the cylindrical paraboloid subreflector of a quadreflex antenna (Ref. 40).

A boron-aluminum landing gear drag link (Ref. 41) for the General Dynamics/U.S. Air Force YF-16 is seen in Figure 24. It weighs 25% less than the equivalent aluminum part. Such structures are also being used in the Space Shuttle Orbiter Fuselage. A boron-epoxy truss for the Space Shuttle engine thrust structure weighs 30% less than the equivalent titanium truss (Ref. 42).

Composites have been used extensively for helicopter rotor blades. In most cases, they are not intended to save weight, but to exploit ease of fabrication of complex airfoil shapes and excellent fatigue resistance. The MBB BO-105 helicopter employs molded fiberglass blades (Ref. 43), as do the Kaman/U.S. Air Force HH-43, the Aerospatiale SA-341, and the Boeing/U.S. Army YUH-61 UTTAS helicopters. The largest such structure under development is the Boeing/U.S. Army Heavy Lift Helicopter blade (Ref. 44) which is 40 feet long. A boron-epoxy rotor blade for the Boeing/U.S. Army CH-47 helicopter was developed and successfully test flown (Ref. 45).

FIG. 23 - THE GRAPHITE-EPOXY TRUSS ON THE APPLICATIONS TECHNOLOGY SATELLITE IS HALF THE WEIGHT OF A METAL TRUSS. HERCULES PHOTO

FIG. 24 - BORON-ALUMINUM LANDING GEAR DRAG LINK FOR THE YF-16. GENERAL DYNAMICS PHOTO

A unique application of composites to rotors is the Sikorsky/U.S. Army YUH-60A bearingless tail rotor, seen in Figures 25 and 26, which exploits the anisotropic properties of the unidirectional spar to allow pitch change without bearings (Refs. 21, 46, 47). A unidirectional graphite-epoxy spar extends from the tip of one blade,

through the hub, to the tip of the opposite blade. The spar has high centrifugal strength and bending stiffness, but its very low torsional stiffness allows it to be twisted over its free length between the hub and torque transfer rib to accomplish blade pitch change without a bearing. In addition to simplifying the rotor system considerably and, therefore, improving reliability and reducing cost, the fact that the hub does not have to carry the blade centrifugal loads allows it to be simple and light. The rotor system is 40% below the weight of a conventional hinged rotor system.

FIG. 25 - THE COMPOSITE BEARING-LESS ROTOR EXPLOITS THE ANISOTROPY OF COMPOSITES.

FIG. 26 - THE GRAPHITE AND GLASS-EPOXY TAIL ROTOR ON THE YUH-60A UTTAS HELICOPTER. SIKORSKY AIRCRAFT PHOTO.

The Sikorsky/U.S. Navy H-3 twin beam composite main rotor blade (Refs. 46, 48, 49) is seen in Figure 27. The construction consists of $\pm 45^\circ$ graphite-epoxy to carry torsional loads, co-cured with 0° glass-epoxy to carry centrifugal and bending loads. The blade was designed to be made in two halves for ease of manufacture, as seen in Figure 28. The allowable large dimensional tolerances of each step are additive and are removed when each half is machined to the chord line, thus providing a low-cost blade. Filament winding is another low-cost manufacturing technique that has been applied to rotor blades (Ref. 50). This technique has been used to construct experimental blades for the Bell/U.S. Army UH-1D, the Hughes/U.S. Army OH-6A, and the Boeing/U.S. Army Heavy Lift Helicopter.

Composites have been used in gas turbine engines to a limited extent. Several developmental fan blade programs (Refs. 51-53) have demonstrated the potential for 40 to 50% weight saving plus 1% increase in efficiency by elimination of part-span shrouds (clappers). Commitment to production has been delayed by the problems of foreign object impact damage demonstrated so dramatically during development of the Rolls-Royce RB-211 engine. This problem is apparently being overcome by improved protection of the leading

edge and use of more impact-resistant laminates. Advanced development of eutectic composites for applications in the hottest parts of the turbine promise improved efficiency by increasing allowable metal temperatures (Refs. 54, 55).

FIG. 27 - THE TWIN BEAM COMPOSITE ROTOR IS MADE IN TWO HALVES AND BONDED TOGETHER.

FIG. 29 - THE GRAPHITE ATLAS MISSILE BULKHEAD IS 25% LIGHTER THAN A METAL BULKHEAD. GENERAL DYNAMICS PHOTO.

FIG. 28 - THE UNIQUE TWO-PIECE CONSTRUCTION OF THE TWIN BEAM BLADE PERMITS SIMPLIFIED FABRICATION AND TOOLING.

FIG. 30 - GRAPHITE F-5 CENTER SECTION IS A MAJOR ADVANCE IN COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT. GENERAL DYNAMICS PHOTO.

The first production commitment of the use of advanced composites for gas turbine engines is for the fan exit guide vanes of the Pratt and Whitney Aircraft JT9D-59 and JT9D-70 engines, which will power versions of the Boeing 747 and Douglas DC-10 (Ref. 56). The graphite epoxy vanes are 60% lighter than their aluminum counterparts, provide improved efficiency by virtue of a smaller chord and thickness, and exhibit superior fatigue resistance.

Current development of fuselage structures emphasizes cost reduction as well as weight reduction. The graphite Atlas missile bulkhead (Ref. 57), seen in Figure 29, is 25% lighter than its aluminum counterpart and was manufactured for the same recurring cost. Under U.S. Air Force sponsorship, General Dynamics (Ft. Worth Division) has developed two generations of large molded composite fuselage structure. The first was a 160-inch long section of the F-111 aft fuselage made with molded and sandwich configurations of graphite/epoxy, boron/epoxy, boron/aluminum, and glass/epoxy (Ref. 58). Internal structures were built first, and the skins were attached later, as in metal construction. The next generation structure built was the F-5 center fuselage (Ref. 59), seen in Figure 30 next to the production aircraft. For this structure, which is primarily graphite/epoxy, a one-piece skin was molded for each of the upper and lower halves, and the internal structure was subsequently bonded or mechanically fastened to the interior of the shell. Because both development program emphasized weight saving - 18% for the F-111 part and 26% for the F-5 component - the production costs were projected to be higher than the metal production components. The concept of building large molded shells and inserting the substructure, however, promises lower production costs than metal fuselage structures. Such technology is being developed for the General Dynamics/U.S. Air Force YF-16 (Ref. 60) and the Northrop/U.S. Air Force YF-17 (Ref. 61).

The cost reduction potential for the shell and liner concept can be improved substantially if both are molded together in one step. This process has been demonstrated on the production Sikorsky H-53 helicopter cockpit canopy, as seen in Figure 19, and the concept is currently being extended to save weight and cost for the major portion of the fuselage (Ref. 62). It should be noted that the labor cost reduction of nearly two-thirds experienced for the cockpit canopy would probably not be as great for the remainder of the fuselage. The cockpit canopy is lightly loaded and contains complex curvature, so both factors favor molded structure. Nevertheless, the concept of molding large components and minimizing the assembly labor of many small pieces makes inroads into the major portion of the cost, which is labor, and allows use of more expensive materials for cost competitive structures.

Graphite composite structures have been used for the YF-16 and YF-17 prototypes. The YF-17 (Ref. 63, 64) uses 900 pounds of graphite, as seen in Figure 31, and 200 pounds of aramid components.

The result has been a direct weight saving of 360 pounds compared with equivalent metal structure and, because of the growth factor, a total system weight saving of more than 500 pounds. These composite structures are now cost effective and are expected to be cost competitive in production applications. The YF-16 also contains a variety of cost-effective graphite structures, but the details have not yet been released.

FIG. 31 - THE PROTOTYPE YF-17 STRUCTURE IS 10% GRAPHITE. FIGURE COURTESY OF NORTHROP CORP.

FIG. 32 COMMERCIAL USAGE OF COMPOSITES IS INCREASING RAPIDLY, ESPECIALLY FOR SPORTING GOODS SUCH AS THIS RACING BICYCLE FRAME. HERCULES PHOTO

Commercial Applications

Commercial applications now dominate the market for composite materials. Such applications include golf club shafts, tennis racquets, fishing rods, archery bows, arrows, bicycle frames (Figure 32), skis and poles, hockey sticks, textile and packaging machine components, and gears and bearings. In 1973, more than one-half million golf clubs with composite shafts were produced (Ref. 65). The primary motivation is a 30% reduction in shaft weight, which allows additional weight to be added to the head to improve performance. By using the damping characteristics of graphite-epoxy, a javelin has been developed with reduced aerodynamic drag (Ref. 65) and now is setting new distance records. Graphite and glass-reinforced plastic racing car components have been developed that are less than one-fourth the weight of steel (Ref. 65). The winning cars at the Indianapolis 500 Race for the past several years have had graphite-reinforced bodies.

Graphite and boron composites have been used for components of the twelve-meter sailing yacht Intrepid, which was the successful defender of the America Cup in 1970 (Ref. 66). Kevlar fiber has been used extensively for racing canoes and kayaks, sailboats, surfboards, and paddles, because of improved weight, stiffness, and impact properties (Ref. 67).

Applications of composites to textile and other highspeed machinery components are motivated by the potential for improved life and increased machine speed. Graphite picking sticks for weaving looms last 3 to 10 times longer than wooden sticks and allow higher operating speeds, resulting in 25 to 30 percent increases in productivity (Ref. 65). By reinforcing the needle, sinker, and guide bars of a knitting machine with graphite, productivity increases of 25 to 40 percent have been demonstrated (Ref. 65). Improved performance is also claimed for graphite faller bars for gilling machines, because of lighter weight, better lubrication characteristics, and improved dissipation of static charge, which causes debris to cling to the steel faller (Ref. 65).

Graphite-epoxy, Kevlar-epoxy, and glass-epoxy have been used to construct the stretcher table of a diagnostic X-ray simulator used in cancer treatment (Ref. 68). These materials were selected to provide the stiffness required for the cantilevered structure and meet the maximum radiation attenuation requirements.

Kevlar filament is being used for ropes and cables, because its strength-to-density ratio is seven times higher than that of steel. Where long lengths are required, the ability of the cable to support its own weight is a prime consideration. The maximum Kevlar cable length can be seven times that of steel in air, and 26 times that of steel in water. In 1972, a large portion of a radio telescope in Puerto Rico was constructed with Kevlar cables because of its strength, stiffness, and dielectric constant (Ref. 69). Kevlar cables are also being considered for helicopter cargo hoist and towing systems.

Future Developments

Although aerospace applications can be said to have developed and dominated the composites market, the total tonnage of material used in recent years has been greater for non-aerospace applications. This has had a salutary effect on the cost of material, but while the sporting goods market is nearing saturation the aerospace market has great growth potential. When the current inhibitions concerning manufacturing cost, reliability, and maintenance are resolved, there will be extensive use in aerospace. Within one or two decades at most, barring discovery of a fatal flaw, composites will constitute the majority of the structural weight of aircraft. The all-composite Windecker Eagle, seen in Figure 33, is a harbinger of future aircraft construction.

FIG. 33 - THE ALL-COMPOSITE WINDECKER "EAGLE" IS AN INDICATION OF THE FUTURE OF AIRCRAFT CONSTRUCTION. WINDECKER AIRCRAFT PHOTO.

The technological developments necessary to remove the manufacturing cost barrier are well underway. This involves a shift in emphasis from designing for maximum structural efficiency to designing for cost. The design team must begin with demonstrated or emerging low-cost concepts, such as pultrusion, filament winding, automated broadgoods lay-up, vacuum injection molding, fibre-reinforced thermoplastics, or use of woven material, and design structures that can be made simply. Reducing the number of sub-assemblies and manufacturing steps is an important consideration in meeting the goal of lower cost. The shift away from adhesively bonded attachments to reliable mechanical attachments will help achieve this goal, because many early design concepts were dominated by the need for large bond attachment areas.

Major material problems that still remain are the variability of the basic materials, proliferation of products, and lack of industry standards. The shift from development to production should provide the impetus to solve these problems. Machining and fastening costs do not appear to be a problem. With the exception of boron, composites can be machined at less cost than metals (Ref. 19). Fastening problems can be overcome by careful matching of fastener stiffness with laminate stiffness and by using inserts, such as washers, to prevent local crushing during riveting.

The technology needed to provide adequate assessment of reliability and maintenance cost and risk is slow in developing. It probably represents the greatest barrier to extensive use of composites in aircraft. A large financial commitment will be required to put demonstration structures in service, and time in service will be required to uncover the unpredictable surprises that accompany introduction of any new technology. Both the U.S. military and the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration are moving to achieve this goal in the 1970's and early 1980's (Ref. 70). Because composites are essentially free from corrosion, a major maintenance cost item for metal aircraft, they should require less maintenance. This factor, however, will require extended service experience to quantify.

We now have ample test and service experience to indicate that composite structures are safer and more reliable than metals. Many composites structures have demonstrated good damage tolerance and slow damage propagation, and the design techniques that lead to this improved reliability are beginning to be understood and defined. Because cracking is not the dominant damage mode in composites, it will be necessary to relate nondestructive inspection measurements, other than crack detection techniques used for metals, to residual strength and life characteristics of the structure. For this purpose, ultrasonics, holography, acoustic emission, thermal methods, and stiffness measurements appear to offer sufficient capability.

The future use of composite materials appears to be very promising, provided sufficient technical and financial resources can be committed to surmount the remaining technological and psychological barriers. The benefits, in terms of improved performance and reduced costs, are sufficiently large that such commitments are justified and are beginning to be made.

The potential in aerospace applications is great. Less obvious, but of greater potential, are commercial transportation systems - automobiles, trucks, trains, and people movers. The emphasis on weight reduction to reduce fuel consumption and on manufacturing cost reduction will provide the drive toward composites. And what of static structures - buildings and bridges? Low-cost modular construction using composites is emerging for buildings, and they don't corrode or rot. Why not make bridges of non-metallic materials and avoid the cost of continuous repainting? The use of composites for medical applications is beginning. Composite prostheses are less than half the weight of metal devices. What a boon to the person who must carry that weight with him all day.

The challenge to fulfill this potential clearly rests with the engineering and manufacturing professions. We must mount a cooperative concerted effort to utilize the limited available resources most effectively in order to bring composite structures technology to its full potential.

References

1. L. Lackman, "Advanced Composites Design Guide" Third Edition, Air Force Materials Lab, Ohio, January 1973.
2. J. Ashton, J. Halpin, and P. Petit, Primer on Composite Materials: Analysis, Technomic, Stamford, 1969.
3. M. Salkind and G. Holister, eds, Applications of Composite Materials, STP524, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1973.
4. Composite Materials: Testing and Design, STP460, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1969.
5. Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Second Conference), STP497, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1972.
6. Analysis of Test Methods for High Modulus Fibers and Composites, STP521, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1973.
7. Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Third Conference), STP546, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1974.
8. L. Broutman and R. Krock, eds, Modern Composite Materials, Addison-Wesley, Reading, Mass. 1967.
9. E. Scala, Composite Materials For Combined Functions, Hayden, Rochelle Pk. New Jersey, 1973.
10. S. Tsai, J. Halpin, and N. Pagano, Composite Materials Workshop, Technomic, Stamford, 1968.
11. G. Sendeckyj, ed, Mechanics of Composite Materials, Vol. 2 of Composite Materials, Academic Press, New York, 1974.
12. L. Broutman, ed, Fracture and Fatigue, Vol. 5 of Composite Materials, Academic Press, New York, 1974.
13. C. Chamis, ed., Structural Design and Analysis - Part I, Vol. 7 of Composite Materials, Academic Press, New York, 1974.
14. C. Chamis, ed. Structural Design and Analysis - Part II, Vol. 8 of Composite Materials, Academic Press, New York, 1975.
15. MIL-HDBK-17A, Department of Defense, Washington, D.C., January 1971.
16. D. Oplinger, B. Parker, and F. Chiang, Experimental Mechanics, Vol. 14, Sept. 1974, pp. 347-354.

17. J. Sainsbury-Carter, Trans ASME, J. Eng. Ind., Vol. 95, Ser B, No. 4, Nov. 1973, pp. 919-924.
18. M. Rich and R. Welge, AIAA paper 72-392, Presented at the 13th SDM Conference, San Antonio, April 1972.
19. H. Schjelderup, and D. Purdy, Air World, No. 3, 1972, pp. 64-69.
20. M. Salkind, ref. 5, pp. 143-169.
21. K. Hanby, MCIC Review of Metals Technology, Battelle, Columbus, Oct. 11, 1974.
- 22a. Proceedings of the Conference on Fibrous Composites in Flight Vehicle Design, AFFDL-TR-72-130, Air Force Flight Dynamics Lab, Ohio, Sept. 1972.
- 22b. Proceedings of the Second Conference on Fibrous Composites in Flight Vehicle Design, AFFDL-TR-74-103, Air Force Flight Dynamics Lab, Ohio, Sept. 1974.
23. Materials and Processes for the 70's, SAMPE, Azusa, California, 1973.
24. Materials on the Move, SAMPE, Azusa, California, 1974.
25. New Industries and Applications for Advanced Materials Technology, SAMPE, Azusa, California, 1974.
26. C. Rogers, "Structural Design with Composites", Fundamental Aspects of Fiber Reinforced Plastics, ed. by R. Schwartz and H. Schwartz, Wiley, N.Y. 1968, pp. 141-160.
27. G. Lubin and S. Dastin, "First Boron Composite Structural Production Part", 26th SPI Conference Proceedings, Society for the Plastics Ind., N.Y., 1971, Sec. 17-C.
28. G. Lehman and A. Mano, AIAA Paper 72-358, 13th SDM Conference, San Antonio, April 1972.
29. D. Smillie and D. Purdy, "Advanced Material Application to Subsonic Transport Aviation," Douglas Paper 6186, presented at the Ninth Congress of the International Conference of Aeronautical Sciences, Haifa, August 1974.
30. W. Brooks and M. Dow, Reference 23, pp. 539-558.
31. A. Tucci, "Fabrication of Advanced Fibrous Composite Structures," Douglas Paper 6097, presented at the 1973 WESTEC Conference, Los Angeles, March 1973.

32. L. Lassiter, "Applications and Concepts for the Incorporation of Composites in large Military Transport Aircraft," Paper No. 17, Presented at the Royal Aero. Soc. Conference on Reinforced Plastics in Aerospace Applications, The Plastics Institute, London, April 1973.
33. R. June and J. Lager, Reference 3, pp. 1-42.
34. G. Zender and H. Dexter, NASA TN D-4878, 1968.
35. P. Sumida, L. Hart-Smith, R. Pride, and W. Illg. SPI 28th Annual Western Conference, Society for the Plastics Industry, N.Y., 1971, pp. 74-90.
36. D. Dial and M. Howeth, Proceedings of the 16th National SAMPE Symposium, SAMPE, Azusa, California, 1971, pp. 302-314.
37. R. Hadcock, "The Application of Mixed Fiber Composites to Military Aircraft," presented at the 10th National ACS Symposium, Washington, D.C., June 1974.
38. N. Mayer, Reference 23, pp. 559-580.
39. R. Stonier and H. Hillesland, Reference 25, pp. 596-608.
40. E. Robinson, R. Stonier, and C. Lofgren, Reference 7, pp. 632-650.
41. A. Robertson and M. Miller, Reference 24, pp. 361-368.
42. W. Ludwig and J. Sicari, Reference 23, pp.336-355.
43. E. Jarosch and A. Stepan, Journal of the Americal Helicopter Society, Vol. 15, 1970, pp. 33-41.
44. T. Scarpeti, R. Sandford, and R. Powell, "The Heavy Lift Helicopter Rotor Blade," Preprint No. 710, 29th AHS Forum, American Helicopter Society, N.Y., May 1973.
45. R. Pinckney, Reference 3, pp. 108-133.
46. M. Salkind, "New Composite Helicopter Rotor Concepts," Proceedings of the Conference on Fibrous Composites in Flight Vehicle Design, AFFDL-TR-72-130, Air Force Flight Dynamics Lab, Ohio, September 1972, pp. 57-74.
47. M. Ulitchney and J. Lucas, NASA CR-132414, January 1974.
48. M. Salkind, Fibre Science and Technology, Vol. 8, No. 2, 1975, pp. 92-102.

49. M. Salkind and W. Reinfelder, U.S. Patent 3, 782, 856, Jan. 1, 1974.
50. L. Ashton and I. Figge, Jr., Reference 24, pp. 314-323.
51. S. Sattar, H. Stargardter, and D. Randall, "The Development of JT8D Turbofan Engine Composite Fan Blades," AIAA 69-465, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, N.Y., June 1969.
52. W. Schulz, J. Mangiapane, and H. Stargardter, "Development of BORSIC^R - Aluminum Composite Fan Blades for Supersonic Turbofan Engines," ASME 71-GT-90, American Society for Mechanical Engineers, N.Y., March 28, 1971.
53. I. Petker and W. Holmes, "Boron/Polyimide Fan Blades - A Fabrication Study," SAE 71-0772, Society of Automotive Engineers, N.Y., September, 1971.
54. J. Semmel Jr., Reference 24, pp. 154-167.
55. H. Hauser, Reference 24, pp. 168-177.
56. V. Vitali, Reference 25, pp. 256-261.
57. D. Forest, General Dynamics, San Diego, Private Communication.
58. J. Ashton, M. Burdorf, and F. Olsen, Reference 5, pp. 3-27.
59. P. Shockey, Reference 23, pp. 423-431.
60. J. Fant and D. Jones, Reference 22B, pp. 27-53.
61. D. Stansberger, et.al., "Low Cost Manufacturing Concepts of Advanced Composite Primary Aircraft Structures," Second Quarterly Report, Contract F33615-74-C-5153, November 1974.
62. M. Rich, G. Ridgley, & D. Lowry, "Application of Advanced Composites to Helicopter Airframe Structures," Preprint No. 880, 30th National Forum. American Helicopter Society, N.Y., May, 1974.
63. H. Click, Reference 24, pp. 352-360.
64. R. Hayes, Application of Advances in Structures and Materials to the Design of the YF-17 Airplane," Paper No. 730891, Society of Automotive Engineers, N.Y., October 1973.
65. J. DeVault, "Commercial Applications for Graphite Reinforced Composites." SAMPE Quarterly, Vol. 5, No. 2, Jan. 1974. pp. 10-16.

66. K. Marshall, "High Strength Composites for America Cup Defenders", 26th SPI Conference Proceedings, Society for the Plastics Ind., N.Y., 1971, Sec. 7-C.
67. D. Sturgeon, P. Riewald, and R. Lacy, Reference 25, pp. 304-319.
68. P. Leopold, A. Cooper, and J. Arens, Reference 25, pp. 282-290.
69. E. Scala, Reference 6, pp. 390-409.
70. A. Lovelace, "Advanced Composites," von Karman lecture, paper No. 74-242, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, N.Y., Jan. 1974.